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Notes on the Herpetofauna of Sinaloa, Mexico 1: New Geographical Record for the Cora Mud Turtle (*Kinosternon cora*)

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Introduction

It has been less than five years since its original description (Loc-Barragán et al., 2020), and recently the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) has listed the Cora Mud Turtle (*Kinosternon cora*) as Critically Endangered, resulting from major conservation challenges such as illegal traffic for export and the loss of natural aquatic habitats (PROFEPA, 2025; Loc-Barragán et al., in press). To date, only 47 individuals of *K. cora*, from 15 localities, have been found in the wild, providing only data on geographic range and morphometry (Loc-Barragán and Iverson, 2024). The known geographic range is quite restricted, being endemic to the coastal plain of western Mexico in the states of Sinaloa and Nayarit. There are only 15 localities with a range of ca. 8900 km² (TTWG, in press), but the documented area of occupancy (AOO) is only ca. 4100 km². Here we report a new geographical distribution record for *K. cora*.

Distribution Record

MEXICO: SINALOA: Municipio de San Ignacio: Área de Protección de Flora y Fauna Meseta de Cacaxtla (detailed locality data withheld for biosecurity reasons). This mud turtle was found in a tropical deciduous forest with fragments of thorn forest. A photo voucher of the individual (Figure 1) was deposited in the Colección Herpetológica, Universidad Michoacana (CHUM-F423). The specimen was identified as *K. integrum* from 2010 to 2024. In 2025 the fourth author of this work identified the species as *K. cora*, with verification of morphological traits: body size, curvature of the carapace, a narrow bridge,

Figure 1. Photograph by Marco A. González.

a long interfemoral scute seam, a relatively large axillary scute, and the noticeable presence of a rostral shield. These traits clearly differentiate *K. cora* from *K. integrum*. This observation was added to the iNaturalist platform as: <https://mexico.inaturalist.org/observations/162093508>.

Discussion

This report represents the first record for this species from Municipio de San Ignacio Sinaloa and Área de Protección de Flora y Fauna Meseta de Cacaxtla, the northernmost known locality in Mexico and extends the known distribution approximately 117 km northwest from the nearest documented locality (detailed locality data withheld for biosecurity reasons) in Rosario, Sinaloa (Loc-Barragán and Iverson, 2024). The eleva-

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tion and habitat are consistent with where this species has been reported throughout its distribution across the Pacific Coastal plain (Loc-Barragán et al., 2020; Loc-Barragán and Iverson, 2024; Loc-Barragán et al., 2024).

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